

UNVEILING TEACHERS' MOTIVATION OF LEAVING DEPED TO TEACH ABROAD: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY

Razul W. Magonsik, LPT¹
Jaime Boy U, Ngag Jr., Ph.D.²

¹*DEPED Lutayan District II, Sultan Kudarat Division, Philippines*

²*South Cotabato State College, South Cotabato, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The migration of teachers from their home countries to pursue teaching opportunities abroad is a growing phenomenon that has significant implications for both the countries of origin and the host nations. Many teachers have opted to leave their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to seek better financial opportunities, career advancement, and improved working conditions overseas. Understanding the motivations behind this decision is essential for addressing the issues of teacher retention and brain drain within the education sector. This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of teachers who have left DepEd to teach abroad, delving into the factors that influenced their decisions and the potential impact on the local educational system in Lutayan District II, Sultan Kudarat Division. The trend of teachers leaving DepEd for overseas opportunities has been particularly noticeable. The region faces unique socio-economic challenges, including limited resources, large student-to-teacher ratios, and low wages compared to more urbanized areas in the Philippines. This study employed a qualitative research design, particularly narrative inquiry. The participants of this study were the selected ten (10) teachers who chose to teach abroad, who qualified the inclusion criteria set by the researcher through Purposive Sampling Technique of Creswell (2013). A semi-structured interview was utilized in this study as an exploratory tool used during the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) which protocols were adopted from the study of Ngag (2023). This instrument was validated by the panel of evaluators who are experts in the construction of relevant instruments. All gathered raw data from the participants through interview and FGD were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). A thematic or content analysis

patterned after Clark and Braun (2006) was used to analyze the transcribed data from the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The results reveal that teachers are motivated to leave DepEd for higher salaries, better work environments, and access to advanced technology abroad. Factors such as professional development opportunities, cultural experiences, dissatisfaction with DepEd, family considerations, and improved work-life balance also play significant roles. International teaching environments offer higher pay, less stressful workloads, better resources, and more opportunities for career growth and personal fulfillment. Financial considerations, such as higher salaries and better benefits, dominate migration decisions, complemented by professional growth opportunities and personal aspirations like family reunification. While some teachers excel abroad, others face adjustment challenges, with the migration of experienced educators contributing to a brain drain in the Philippines. Teachers abroad report better recognition, appreciation, and financial stability compared to the stressful workloads and limited recognition in DepEd. In conclusion, teacher migration highlights the need for DepEd to address financial, professional, and systemic issues to improve teacher retention and the quality of education. The stark contrast in working conditions and career prospects underscores the challenge of retaining skilled educators within the country.

Keywords: *Teacher Migration, DepEd Challenges, Motivational Factors, Brain Drain, Professional Growth*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The migration of teachers from their home countries to pursue teaching opportunities abroad is a growing phenomenon that has significant implications for both the countries of origin and the host nations. In the Philippines, particularly in the South-Central Mindanao region, many teachers have opted to leave their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to seek better financial opportunities, career advancement, and improved working conditions overseas. Understanding the motivations behind this decision is essential for addressing the issues of teacher retention and brain drain within the education sector.

Globally, teacher migration has been driven by a combination of economic, professional, and personal factors. In countries like the United States, Canada, and the United Arab Emirates, there is a high demand for skilled educators, particularly in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields, as well as for English language teachers (Lipiński & Burke, 2021). Studies have shown that teachers from developing countries, including the Philippines, are attracted to these opportunities due to higher salaries, better working conditions, and more professional development opportunities (Poole, 2020). However, the literature reveals a gap in understanding how these international experiences influence returning teachers' professional growth and re-integration into their home countries' education systems.

In the Philippines, the exodus of teachers to foreign countries has become an increasing concern. According to the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA), thousands of Filipino teachers migrate annually, contributing to a growing teacher shortage in local schools (POEA, 2021). Teachers leave primarily for financial reasons, citing inadequate salaries and heavy workloads as major factors (Cruz & Alamillo, 2019). Despite the growing number of studies on teacher migration, there is limited research that focuses on the specific motivations of teachers leaving DepEd and the personal and professional consequences of such decisions. This gap in literature suggests the need for more focused studies on the motivations and lived experiences of teachers from specific regions like South Central Mindanao.

In South Central Mindanao, the trend of teachers leaving DepEd for overseas opportunities has been particularly noticeable. The region faces unique socio-economic challenges, including limited resources, large student-to-teacher ratios, and low wages compared to more urbanized areas in the Philippines (Ramos et al., 2020). Teachers from this region are often drawn to the prospects of higher income and career advancement abroad. However, there is little research that delves into the specific reasons why teachers from South Central Mindanao decide to leave and how this decision affects the quality of education in the region. The lack of localized studies highlights a significant gap in the literature, especially in understanding how regional factors influence teacher migration motivations.

While there is extensive research on global teacher migration, there remains a notable gap in the literature focusing on the motivations and experiences of Filipino teachers, particularly those from South Central Mindanao. Most studies emphasize economic factors but lack depth in exploring the socio-cultural and personal dimensions of these teachers' decisions to migrate. Furthermore, there is limited research on the long-term impact of teacher migration on the local education systems they leave behind, especially in under-resourced regions like South Central Mindanao. This study seeks to fill this gap by providing a narrative inquiry into the motivations of teachers from this region who leave DepEd to teach abroad.

This study aims to explore the lived experiences of teachers who have left DepEd to teach abroad, delving into the factors that influenced their decisions and the potential impact on the local educational system.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to explore the lived experiences of teachers who have left DepEd to teach abroad, delving into the factors that influenced their decisions and the potential impact on the local educational system in Lutayan District II, Sultan Kudarat Division.

Specifically, this was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the primary factors that motivate teachers to leave DepEd and pursue teaching opportunities abroad?
 2. How do teachers perceive the working conditions and career opportunities in DepEd compared to those in international teaching environments?
 3. In what ways do personal, professional, and financial considerations influence the decision of teachers to migrate and teach abroad?
 4. How do the lived experiences of teachers who have left DepEd to teach abroad reflect the broader trends of teacher migration and brain drain in the Philippine education system?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, particularly narrative inquiry to investigate the experiences and motivations of teachers in the Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have left or are considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad.

Narrative inquiry is a qualitative research method that focuses on the study of individuals' lived experiences as told through their personal stories. It emphasizes the way people create meaning in their lives through narratives, which are considered both a method of communication and a mode of knowing. In narrative inquiry, researchers collect and analyze these stories to gain insights into the participants' perspectives, cultural contexts, and the processes through which they construct their identities and make sense of their experiences (Clandinin and Connelly, 2000).

Respondents of the Study

Table 1 displays the qualifications of the participants based on the criteria set by the researcher prior to the selection of qualified informants of the study.

Table 1

Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Qualifications

Participants: 10 Teachers

Current Employment Status

-Participants must currently be employed as teachers under the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines. This criterion ensures that the study captures the perspectives of teachers who are actively engaged in the local education system and are considering or have considered migration for teaching abroad.

Intent to Migrate or Previous Experience Abroad

Participants should either express a clear intent to migrate and teach abroad or have previously taught in an international setting. This inclusion criterion allows for a diverse range of narratives, providing insights from those contemplating migration as well as those who have firsthand experience with the challenges and motivations associated with teaching abroad.

Minimum Teaching Experience

Participants should have a minimum of three years of teaching experience within the DepEd system. This criterion ensures that participants have sufficient professional experience to articulate their motivations and perspectives regarding teaching both locally and internationally.

Willingness to Participate in Narrative Inquiry

Participants must be willing to share their personal experiences and motivations through narrative inquiry methods, including interviews and focus group discussions.

The participants of this study were the selected ten (10) teachers who chose to teach abroad, who qualify the inclusion criteria set by the researcher.

Sampling Technique

This study employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to purposefully select teachers who left DepEd and taught abroad. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own discretion when selecting population members to participate in their surveys (Ngag, 2023).

This survey sampling method necessitates that researchers have prior knowledge of the purpose of their studies in order to select and approach eligible participants for online survey platforms such as Alchemer (2021). Researchers use purposive sampling to gain access to a specific subset of individuals, as all survey respondents are chosen because they suit a specific profile.

Research Instruments

A semi-structured interview was utilized in this study as an exploratory tool to be used during the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) to explore data regarding experiences and motivations of teachers in the Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have left or are considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad. This instrument was validated by the panel of evaluators who are experts in the construction of relevant instruments.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study's reliability was ensured by the researcher's strict adherence to a set of protocols. The study's focus was to explore the experiences and motivations of teachers in the Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who had left or were considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad. First, the Superintendent of the DepEd-Sultan Kudarat and the Dean of the CGS were requested to sign a document authorizing the researcher to take the necessary steps to conduct the study.

A second authorization letter was sent to the teachers as consent in order to acquire the precise data necessary for the study. A survey questionnaire was created, evaluated, and implemented.

The researcher then chose respondents using a Purposive Sampling Technique to consider all the newly appointed school heads as participants in the study. As long as the health procedure was adhered to, the researcher began distributing the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) via Zoom/Google.

Finally, the data acquired from the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were collated, analyzed, and interpreted using thematic analysis.

Flow Process and Data Gathering Procedure

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interviews and FGDs were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned their transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent narrative analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data.

In the context of the study on the experiences and motivations of teachers in Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who had left or were considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad, the steps in the transcription process were outlined as follows:

Step 1: Audio Recording of Interviews

The first step in the transcription process involved audio recording interviews with the participants. For this study, researchers conducted in-depth interviews with teachers in Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who had left or were considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad. These interviews were recorded with explicit consent from the participants.

Step 2: Verbatim Transcription

Verbatim transcription was crucial as it captured participants' responses exactly as spoken, including pauses, hesitations, and emotional expressions Cerdana and Ngag (2024). The researcher meticulously transcribed the audio recordings, ensuring to preserve the precise language, grammatical structures, and speech patterns of the participants interviewed.

Step 3: Researcher Verification

After transcription, the researcher verified the accuracy of transcripts by carefully reviewing them for any discrepancies or omissions (Ronquillo, & Ngag, 2024). This step ensured that the written text faithfully represented the original audio recordings and maintained the integrity of the data collected.

Step 4: Participant Validation

Following transcription, the researcher shared the transcripts with participants for their review and feedback. Participants had the opportunity to validate the accuracy of their recorded responses, providing insights or clarifications where necessary. This process ensured that participants' perspectives were accurately represented in the study.

Step 5: Anonymization

To protect participants' confidentiality, the researcher anonymized transcripts by replacing any identifying information, such as names or specific locations, with pseudonyms or generic descriptors. This precautionary measure safeguarded the privacy of young learners involved in the study.

Data Analysis

A thematic or content analysis was used to analyze the data. By assigning each text's assertions, phrases, and words to a system or collection of categories—either based on or adapted from existing ones or established from scratch in connection to the study objectives.

Written interview data was collected from the participants to determine the experiences and motivations of teachers in the Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have left or are considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad. The interviews and FGDs conducted for this research will be used to distill the most salient participant answers into overarching themes.

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on exploring the experiences and motivations of teachers in the Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who have left or are considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad. The research is set within the academic school year 2024-2025 and aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the factors driving teachers to seek opportunities outside the country.

The study was conducted in the Lutayan District II, within the Division of Sultan Kudarat. This location has been chosen due to the noticeable number of teachers from the district leaving for teaching opportunities abroad, making it a pertinent area for exploring the underlying motivations of such decisions. The study focused on current and former DepEd teachers in Lutayan District II who have either migrated to teach abroad or are actively pursuing such opportunities. The sample included teachers from various public schools within the district, with different levels of teaching experience, who have resigned or are planning to resign from DepEd.

The study examined teacher migration during the school year 2024-2025, focusing on recent trends, experiences, and decision-making processes that teachers underwent during this time frame. A narrative inquiry approach was employed to capture the personal stories and lived experiences of the teachers. Through interviews and thematic analysis, the study delved into the emotional, professional, and socio-economic reasons that drive teachers to leave DepEd for opportunities abroad. The study is confined to the Lutayan District II within Sultan Kudarat and does not cover other districts or regions within the Philippines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The migration of teachers from their home countries to pursue teaching opportunities abroad is a growing phenomenon that has significant implications for both the countries of origin and the host nations. Many teachers have opted to leave their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to seek better financial opportunities,

career advancement, and improved working conditions overseas. Understanding the motivations behind this decision is essential for addressing the issues of teacher retention and brain drain within the education sector.

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of teachers who have left DepEd to teach abroad, delving into the factors that influenced their decisions and the potential impact on the local educational system in Lutayan District II, Sultan Kudarat Division. The trend of teachers leaving DepEd for overseas opportunities has been particularly noticeable. The region faces unique socio-economic challenges, including limited resources, large student-to-teacher ratios, and low wages compared to more urbanized areas in the Philippines. This study employed a qualitative research design, particularly narrative inquiry. The participants of this study were the selected ten (10) teachers who chose to teach abroad, who qualified the inclusion criteria set by the researcher through Purposive Sampling Technique of Creswell (2013). A semi-structured interview was utilized in this study as an exploratory tool used during the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) which protocols were adopted from the study of Ngag (2023).

This instrument was validated by the panel of evaluators who are experts in the construction of relevant instruments. All gathered raw data from the participants through interview and FGD were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). A thematic or content analysis patterned after Clark and Braun (2006) was used to analyze the transcribed data from the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

The results reveal that teachers are motivated to leave DepEd for higher salaries, better work environments, and access to advanced technology abroad. Factors such as professional development opportunities, cultural experiences, dissatisfaction with DepEd, family considerations, and improved work-life balance also play significant roles. International teaching environments offer higher pay, less stressful workloads, better resources, and more opportunities for career growth and personal fulfillment. Financial considerations, such as higher salaries and better benefits, dominate migration decisions, complemented by professional growth opportunities and personal aspirations like family reunification. While some teachers excel abroad, others face adjustment challenges, with the migration of experienced educators contributing to a brain drain in the Philippines. In the study of Dolutan and Ngag, (2024), it has been revealed that excessive works of teachers contribute to their well-being and satisfaction.

Teachers abroad report better recognition, appreciation, and financial stability compared to the stressful workloads and limited recognition in DepEd. In conclusion, teacher migration highlights the need for DepEd to address financial, professional, and systemic issues to improve teacher retention and the quality of education. The stark contrast in working conditions and career prospects underscores the challenge of retaining skilled educators within the country.

Conclusions

The following inferences were made in light of this study's findings:

Financial and Professional Motivators Drive Teacher Migration: The primary factors motivating teachers to leave DepEd and pursue opportunities abroad include the prospect of higher salaries, better benefits, and improved financial stability. Additionally, opportunities for career growth, professional development, and access to advanced teaching resources in international environments make these options highly attractive to teachers seeking both financial and professional fulfillment.

Perception of Work Conditions in DepEd vs. International Teaching Environments: Teachers perceive the working conditions in DepEd as challenging, with high workloads, large class sizes, and limited resources. In contrast, international teaching environments offer smaller class sizes, better resources, and a more supportive professional infrastructure. This stark difference in working conditions significantly influences teachers' decisions to migrate, as many find the stress and limited recognition in DepEd to be unsustainable.

Personal, Professional, and Financial Considerations Influence Migration Decisions: Teachers' migration decisions are shaped by a combination of personal, professional, and financial factors. Financial incentives, such as higher salaries and benefits, are dominant, but teachers also seek professional growth opportunities, better work-life balance, and improved career prospects. Personal factors like family reunification and the desire for better living conditions also play crucial roles in the decision-making process.

Teacher Migration Contributes to Brain Drain and Educational Gaps: The lived experiences of teachers who migrate abroad reflect broader trends of brain drain in the Philippine education system. As experienced educators leave for better opportunities abroad, the Philippines faces a shortage of skilled teachers, particularly in rural areas. This migration of talent can result in a gap in the quality of education, as less experienced teachers fill the void left by those who migrate.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

For DepEd (Department of Education):

- 1. Increase Salaries and Benefits:** DepEd could push for better salaries and perks for teachers, such as performance bonuses, allowances for special roles, and improved health and retirement plans. This would show teachers that they are valued and help reduce the temptation to look for better opportunities abroad.

2. Support Ongoing Learning and Growth: DepEd can create more opportunities for teachers to grow professionally through training programs, workshops, and access to certifications. Partnering with international institutions and offering online learning options can help teachers develop new skills right where they are, making it easier for them to advance without needing to leave the country.

3. Reduce Workload and Improve Resources: To help ease the pressure on teachers, DepEd should hire more staff to reduce class sizes and lighten teachers' workloads. Providing better teaching resources, like updated textbooks, digital tools, and technology, would make the classroom experience more enjoyable and less stressful for both teachers and students.

For School Administrators:

1. Create a Positive and Supportive Environment: School leaders should make sure teachers feel supported and appreciated. Initiatives like wellness programs, mentoring for new teachers, and stress management workshops can help teachers feel more valued, reducing the chance of burnout and increasing their long-term job satisfaction.

2. Promote Work-Life Balance: Administrators should encourage a balance between work and personal life by offering flexible hours, manageable class sizes, and enough planning time. When teachers have time to recharge, they're more likely to stay in their roles and not seek opportunities abroad.

3. Show Appreciation and Recognition: School leaders should regularly acknowledge and celebrate teachers' hard work. Whether through awards, public recognition, or opportunities for teachers to showcase their achievements, showing teachers that their work is valued can go a long way in keeping them motivated and happy in their roles.

For Future Researchers:

1. Study Effective Teacher Retention Practices: Future research could explore what works in retaining teachers in other countries—whether that's through higher pay, better work conditions, or professional growth opportunities. These studies could give DepEd valuable ideas on how to improve teacher retention in the Philippines.

2. Focus on Areas with Teacher Shortages: Researchers should look into how teacher migration affects rural areas or regions with fewer resources. By pinpointing the regions most in need of teachers, policies can be tailored to help retain staff where they're needed most.

3. Understand What Drives Teacher Migration: Future studies can dig deeper into the personal and professional reasons teachers migrate. Knowing whether it's for financial reasons, career growth, or family matters can help DepEd and schools provide the right kind of support to teachers, keeping them happy and committed to staying.

For Policy Makers:

1. Develop Policies to Retain Teachers: Policymakers may create rules and programs that encourage teachers to stay in the Philippines. This could include offering higher salaries, improving working conditions, and supporting career development to keep teachers motivated and committed to their work.

2. Invest in Teacher Well-being: A national policy focused on teacher well-being—like offering competitive salaries, mental health resources, and family-friendly benefits—would tackle many of the reasons teachers leave. Listening to teachers' concerns and regularly gathering their feedback can also help identify ways to improve their work experience.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to implementation, all of the above plans and suggestions were presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc to ensure compliance with the procedures. In addition, utilizing Informed Consent Forms (see attachments for forms), the researcher ensured that all collected data were voluntarily supplied by qualified individuals who met the study's inclusion criteria. A person who did not want to take part was not coerced or recruited into doing so.

Participants were interviewed, and focus groups were conducted using validated instruments in settings they perceived to be secure, pleasant, and convenient, with risks minimized or eliminated entirely. Participants had the option of reviewing the collected data. Individuals volunteered their time for interviews lasting thirty (30) minutes to one (1) hour.

The participant's time and effort were recognized by the researcher in the form of a token. Consistent with the Data Privacy Act (DPA), the researcher treated all participant data with the utmost confidentiality, guaranteeing that no identifying information about the study's outcomes was shared with any third parties (Ngag, 2023).

Informed Consent: Before participation, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. It was imperative that they possessed a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary, affording participants the autonomy to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any adverse consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality: To safeguard the identities and responses of the students, rigorous measures were enacted to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than using actual names, pseudonyms or codes were employed, upholding the privacy of the participants. The collected data were securely stored with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm: Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and a support system was readily available to assist participants should the need arise.

Researcher-Participant Relationship: The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport when engaging with the school heads. Any actions that might have exploited or caused harm to the participants were scrupulously avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process.

Data Protection: Adherence to data protection regulations and laws was unwaveringly followed to safeguard the personal information of the participants. Stringent measures were employed to ensure the secure storage and transmission of data.

Voluntary Participation: Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was wholly voluntary, devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias: The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might have influenced data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research endeavor.

Institutional Approval: Before initiating the study, the researcher diligently sought ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees.

Honesty and Integrity: The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, devoid of any manipulation or distortion to align with preconceived notions or biases.

Beneficence: The potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, ensuring that the study positively contributed to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity: The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, refraining from imposing external values on the participants.

Inclusion and Diversity: The study's structure prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a wide spectrum of the experiences and motivations of teachers in Lutayan District II, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who had left or were considering leaving their positions in the Department of Education (DepEd) to teach abroad.

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